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Research Article

Design And Evaluation of a Gender-Specific Anti-Ageing Cream for Male Dermatological Needs

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ABSTRACT

Wrinkles, thinning, and roughening of skin are some of the symptoms that affect the skin as it ages. Extrinsic factors that affect skin ageing such as UV radiation can also cause malignant melanoma. Here we selected some herbal ingredients, namely leaves of aloe vera, honey, rice water etc. and investigated their anti-ageing properties. The preparation method is O/W emulsion method in which the Stearic acid, Cetyl Alcohol, Olive Oil is Oil Phase and Honey, Tulsi extract, Aloe vera gel, Rose water, Rice water is Water phase. The formulation is showed a good appearance, and adequate pH, Spreadability, homogeneity, and compatibility were observed. Also, the formulation showed no redness, erythema, and irritation during the irritancy study and they were easily washable. The formulation was stable at room. As artificial creams give many side effects it's better to use cream prepared with natural ingredients as it does not show any side effects but rather is beneficial to the skin. The results demonstrated that the formulated anti-aging creams are safe and usable for the skin. The results showed that the formulation of poly herbal antiaging cream contains all the good characteristics of an ideal cream it was found to be harmless, more effective, easy to manufacture, and more economical compared to synthetic antiaging cream.

INTRODUCTION

Anti-Ageing

Ageing is considered a universal physiological process that is accompanied by systemic changes in the structural integrity of cells that are caused by alterations in metabolic and signal transduction

pathways. Understanding of the biological mechanisms of aging and longevity has grown remarkably over the past two decades. At the molecular level, senescence is strongly associated with susceptibility to chronic diseases and disorders, such as chronic fibrosis, severe atherosclerosis, diabetes, osteoarthritis, and ultimately death. Among the various anti-aging

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methods and preventive strategies, the use of micronutrients or biologically active substances is considered a practical and efficient method that targets a variety of intracellular/extracellular pathways [9].

Ageing

Wrinkles are a by-product of the ageing process. As people age, skin cells divide more slowly, and the middle layer of your skin - the dermis - begins to thin. The dermis has a network of elastin and collagen fibers, which offer support and elasticity. As this network loosens and unravels with time, depressions form on your skin's surface. Aging skin is also less able to retain moisture, less efficient in secreting oil and slower to heal. All of these factors contribute to the development of wrinkles. Excessive exposure to ultraviolet (UV) radiation from the sun can result in Premature aging of your skin, also known as photoaging. Exposure to UV light breaks down collagen fibers and leads to the production of abnormal elastin. When ultraviolet light damages skin tissue, your body produces an enzyme called metalloproteinase. This enzyme creates and reforms collagen. During the process, however, some healthy collagen fibers receive damage, resulting in solar elastosis - the disorganized formation of fibers. Wrinkles develop when the rebuilding process occurs over and over, less efficiently each time. Healthy skin constantly regenerates. Old collagen breaks down and removes itself from your body, which makes room for new collagen. Researchers found that smoking causes a reduction in the production of new collagen. Decreased collagen results in the development of wrinkles.

Anti-Ageing Cream

Skin aging is the result of a continual deterioration process because of damage to cellular DNA and

protein. The aging process is classified into two distinct types, i.e. "sequential skin aging" and "photo-aging". Both types have distinct clinical and historical features. Sequential skin aging is a universal and predictable process characterized by physiological alteration in skin function. In the aging process keratinocytes are unable to form a functional stratum corneum and the rate of formation from neutral lipids slows down, resulting in dry pale skin with wrinkles. In contrast, photoaging is caused by overexposure to UV rays from sunlight. It is characterized by dry, pale, and shallow skin, displaying fine wrinkles as well as deep furrows caused by the disorganization of epidermal and dermal components associated with elastosis and dermatitis. Herbs and plants have already proved useful as a tool in complementary medicine. Cosmetic products are used to protect the skin against exogenous and endogenous harmful agents and enhance the beauty and attractiveness of the skin [1]. The use of cosmetics not only develops an attractive external appearance but towards achieving longevity of good health by reducing skin disorders [1]. The synthetic or natural ingredients present in skin care formulation supports the health, texture, and integrity of skin, moisturizing, and maintaining elasticity of the skin by reduction of type I collagen and photoprotection etc. This property of cosmetics is due to the presence of ingredients in skin care formulations because it helps to reduce the production of free radicals in the skin and manage the skin properties for a long time. Cosmetic products are the best choice to reduce skin disorders such as hyperpigmentation, skin aging, skin wrinkling, rough skin texture etc. The demand for herbal cosmetics is rapidly expanding

Human Skin

The skin is the outer covering of the body. It is the largest organ of the integumentary system. The skin has multiple layers of ectodermal tissue and guards the underlying muscles, bones, ligaments and internal organs. Human skin is similar to that of most other mammals, except that it is not protected by a pelt. Though nearly all human skin is covered with hair follicles, it appears hairless. There are two general types of skin, hairy and

globous skin. The adjective cutaneous means “of the skin”. Skin plays a key role in protecting (the body) against pathogens and excessive water loss. Its other functions are insulation, temperature regulation, sensation, synthesis of vitamin D, and the protection of vitamin B folates. Severely damaged skin will try to heal by forming scar tissue [7].

SKIN ANATOMY

Fig.5 Skin Structure

Skin Components:

Skin has mesodermal cells, pigmentation, or melanin provided by melanocytes, which absorb some of the potentially dangerous ultraviolet radiation (UV) in sunlight. It also contains DNA-repair enzymes that help reverse UV damage, and people who lack the genes for these enzymes suffer high rates of skin cancer. One form predominantly produced by UV light, malignant melanoma, is particularly invasive, causing it to spread quickly, and can often be deadly. Skin pigmentation varies among populations in a striking manner.

Functions of Skin:

Skin performs the following functions:

Protection: an anatomical barrier from pathogens and damage between the internal and external environment in bodily defence, Langerhans cells in the skin are part of the adaptive immune system.

Sensation: contains a variety of nerve endings that react to heat and cold, touch, pressure, vibration, and tissue injury, see somatosensory system and haptics.

Heat regulation: the skin contains a blood supply far greater than its requirements which allows precise control of energy loss by radiation, convection and conduction. Dilated blood vessels increase perfusion and heat loss, while constricted vessels greatly reduce cutaneous blood flow and conserve heat.

Control of evaporation: the skin provides a relatively dry and semi-impermeable barrier to fluid loss. Loss of this function contributes to the massive fluid loss in burns.

Aesthetics and communication: others see our skin and can assess our mood, physical state and attractiveness.

Storage and synthesis: acts as a storage centre for lipids and water, as well as a means of synthesis of vitamin D by action of UV on certain parts of the skin.

Water resistance: The skin acts as a water resistant barrier so essential nutrients aren't washed out of the body.

Skin Layers

- Skin is composed of three primary layers:
- The epidermis, which provides waterproofing and serves as a barrier to infection.
- The dermis, which serves as a location for the appendages of skin.
- The hypodermis subcutaneous adipose layer.

Layers of Epidermis

Epidermis is divided into several layers where cells are formed through mitosis at the innermost layers. They move up the strata changing shape and composition as they differentiate and become filled with keratin. They eventually reach the top layer called stratum corneum. This process is called keratinization and takes place within weeks. The outermost layer of the epidermis consists of 25 to 30 layers of dead cells.

Sub layers Epidermis is divided into the following 5 sub layers or strata:

- Stratum corneum
- Stratum lucidum
- Stratum granulosum
- Stratum spinosum
- Stratum germinativum

Herbal Components Used for Preparing Anti-Ageing Cream

Olive Oil (*Olea europaea*)

Kingdom: Plantae

Family: Oleaceae

Genus: Olea

Species: *O. europaea*

Olive tree is a traditional plant whose fruits (*Olea europaea L.*) are used for olive oil production, especially in Mediterranean countries. These agro-industrial by-products have the potential to be used with different purposes, providing economical advantage. In particular, the field of skin care products and cosmetics may benefit from these remaining materials, as those bioactive compounds can fulfill a real cosmetic function and activity. This review presents the composition of the different olive by-products and their bioactive compounds. The possible application of these wastes as cosmetic ingredients was critically reviewed. Olive trees are usually native to the Mediterranean countries, but their growth has spread globally during the past two decades due to the health benefits attributed to olive oil consumption [10].

Fig.8 Olive Oil

Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum linn*)

Kingdom: Plantae

Class: Magnoliopsida

Family: Lamiaceae

Genus: Ocimum

Species: *O. tenuiflorum*

Ocimum sanctum Linn., commonly known as Krishna tulsi, is a tree of the family Labiatae. Ayurveda was the primary to bring the Krishna tulsi leaf antimicrobial, antifungal, antibacterial, and antioxidant constituents to the notice of chemists for natural and erect, herbaceous, much-branched, softy hairy, biennial or triennial plant, 30-75 cm high. Most species have pinnate green leaves. Blooms naturally occur in purple or reddish flowers and produce tiny rust-colored fruit. Tulsi is preeminent, and a research project is now confirming its beneficial effects. There's mounting evidence that tulsi can address physical, chemical, metabolic, and psychological stress through a singular combination of pharmacological actions [11].

Fig.9 Tulsi Leaves

Aloe vera (*Aloe barbadensis miller*)

Kingdom: Plantae

Family: Liliaceae

Species: Genus Aloe

The use of aloe vera in skincare is no surprise as it's a well-known plant that has been a successful, effective skincare ingredient for a long time. The plant offers great benefits for the skin and hair and its properties have been recognized for thousands of years in traditional medicine; its use has been recorded as early as 2,200 BC, and is associated with important historical characters such as Cleopatra and Alexander the Great.

Aloe vera is also a popular plant for scientific research with many studies being conducted to investigate its properties and composition. Among more than 400 species of aloe, Aloe vera Burm is one of the most prevalent and widely used. It can also be found under Aloe Barbadensis Miller and both names refer to the same plant.

Fig.10 Aloe Vera

Aloe vera leaves have two distinct parts:

the outer green peel; and the inner colorless gel. Just be careful not to confuse the bitter yellow liquid (exudate) from the outer peel with the clear inner gel. Both parts have different components and activities so it's very important to distinguish between them and choose the appropriate part of the aloe vera plant depending on the properties you intend to add to your cosmetic [12].

Rice Water

Kingdom: Plantae

Family: Poaceae

Species: Oryzasativa

Genus: Oryza

Rice (*Oryza sativa*) extract and other natural components are used to make rice face cream a form of facial moisturizer. Due to its many skin-friendly properties, including its capacity to moisturize, brighten, and shield the skin from environmental damage, rice has been utilized in

skincare treatments for ages. Rice extract has antioxidant capabilities in addition to having elements that can aid to improve the tone and texture of the skin [13].

Fig.11 Rice Water

Rose (*Rosa rubiginosa*)

Kingdom: Plantae

Class: Eudicot

Order: Rosales

Family: Rosaceae

Genus: Rosa

Species: Rubiginosa

Rosa gallica petals (RPE) on skin whitening and anti-wrinkle activity. Indicate that RPE evokes skin whitening and anti-wrinkle formation activity by regulating intracellular signalling, supporting its utility as an ingredient for skin whitening and anti-wrinkle cosmetic products. The genus *Rosa* is a large taxon consisting of many species and thousands of cultivars, particularly due to extensive spontaneous hybridization that generates new speciation. The subgenus *Rosa* comprises about 180 species characterized by a variety of colors and scents. These woody perennials are cultivated for multiple purposes, such as cut flowers, outdoor and indoor plants, and fragancing and flavoring in many industries

(perfume, personal care and food sectors mainly) [14].

Fig.12 Rose Petals

Honey (*Apismellifera*)

Family: Apidae

Genus: Apis Linnaeus

Species: Apis Mellifera

Fig.13 Honey

Honey is a natural ingredient for anti-aging that nurtures, protects, and promotes a youthful appearance without the nasty side effects many people experience with conventional skincare products. Honey is also a great source of vital nutrients for the skin, including vitamins and minerals. It contains gluconic acid and amino acids to nourish the skin on a cellular level, helping to repair damage and slow down the signs of aging. Aging skin often becomes drier and loses some of

its youthful plumpness, which can make fine lines and wrinkles more noticeable. Honey is a natural humectant that draws moisture from the air and prevents moisture loss from dry skin, leaving it softer, smoother, and plumper so fine lines and wrinkles are less visible.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The plants for the study were selected, procured from market shade dried, powdered coarsely, and extracted with the hydro-alcoholic solution and used for the formulation The plant materials used for the study are.

Raw Material

Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients (API)

- Honey was purchased from a grocery shop.
- Rice water was collected in a laboratory of college.

Excipients

- Tulsi Leaves Extract was collected from a laboratory of college.
- Aloe vera gel (Aloe vera) was taken from LMCP garden.
- Steric acid was purchased from S.D fine chem. Pvt Ltd.
- Glycerol was purchased from S.D fine chem. Pvt Ltd.
- Dry Rose Petal was purchased from Haleem general store
- Cetyly alcohol was purchased from S.D fine chem. Pvt Ltd.
- Olive oil was purchased from S.D fine chem. Pvt Ltd.

Method of Preparation

Extraction of Tulsi Leaves: Firstly, collect the tulsi leaves from the garden of college. Then they

heat on the heating mantle for the obtaining extract of tulsi leaves. After heating separate the tulsi extract and waste leaves of Tulsi have a anti-oxidant property.

Preparation of Rice Water:

Firstly, taken some amount of rice and heated on the heating mantle for few minutes. After heat take some amount *Rice* of water of the rice for the formulation.

Water Preparation by Three Different Procedures

- **Water prepared by the boiling process (RWB):** 400 g of paddy rice whole grains were boiled in 1 L of deionized water for 30 min. Rice water was filtered through cotton gaze and frozen at -30°C until used.
- **Water prepared with the intact grain (RWM):** 400 g of paddy rice whole grains were mixed with 1 L of deionized and left to shake, at room temperature, for 24 h. Rice water was then filtered through cotton gaze and frozen at -30°C until used.
- **Water prepared with the crushed grain (RWS):** 400 g of paddy rice grains were grinded into smaller pieces using a kitchen robot, for 10 s, mixed with 1 L of deionized water and left to shake, at room temperature, for 24 h. Rice water was then filtered through cotton gaze and frozen at -30°C until used.

Procedure:

- Firstly, maintained all instruments and ingredients of formulation. Instruments should be washed by water.
- Took aloe vera leaves from garden and separated the gel from leaves then gel crush in grinder for fine particles because we need

smaller particles to increase the surface area for easy mixing with solvent and efficient extraction of compounds.

- Then weighed all ingredients by weighing balance.
- After weighed all ingredients dissolved in water phase which ingredients soluble in water phase.
- Oil phase soluble ingredients dissolved in oil phase.
- Then both phases are heated on the heating mantle for few minutes.
- After heat the oil phase solvent is mixed in water phase solvent by continuous stirr into the mortar pestle.
- After mixing triturated the solvent for 30 min.
- Finally herbal anti-ageing cream is prepared and after prepare evaluate them.

Evaluation of Poly Herbal Anti-Ageing Cream

- **Visual appearance:** The physical appearance of prepared formulations was evaluated for their state, colour, odor, and texture.
- **pH:** The pH meter was calibrated using a standard buffer solution. About 0.5g of the cream weighed and dissolved in 50.0ml of distilled water and its pH was measured by pH paper.
- **Spreadability Test:** Spreadability of the system is essential to provide sufficient doses to be taken in from pores and skin to get a proper healing response.
- **Washability Test:** The removal of the cream applied on the skin was done by washing under tap water with minimal force to remove the cream.
- **Irritation test:** Cream shows no redness, irritation, oedema, or inflammation during

irritation studies. These formulations are safe to use for the skin.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Composition of Herbal Anti-Aging Cream

Table: Composition of herbal anti-aging cream

Composition	Quantity for 100 gm (in%)
Honey	1 %
Tulsi Extract	3 %
Aloe vera gel	10 %
Rose Petals	2.5 %
Olive oil	10 %
Cetyl Alcohol	5%
Stearic acid	10 %
Glycerol	5 %
Rose water	Qs

Physical Evaluation:

Table.2 Physical Evaluation of Herbal Anti-Aging Cream

Physical evaluation	
State	Semisolid
Colour	Off White
Odor	Flowery
Texture	Creamy
Consistency	Good

P^H of Anti-Aging Cream

The pH of anti-aging cream was found to be 6 [16].

Fig: pH of Anti-ageing cream

Homogeneity:

The Homogeneity of Anti-Aging cream was found to be Good [16].

Fig.18 Homogeneity of Antiaging cream

Spreadability Test

1 gm sample was placed between the two glass slides and weight was placed on the glass slide for 5 min to compress the sample to a uniform thickness. The time in seconds required to separate the two slides was taken as a measure of spread ability. The Spread ability of Anti-Aging cream was found to be 10.23(gm. cm/sec) [16].

Fig: Spreadability Test

Washability Test

The Anti-ageing cream was easily and readily washable under tap water.

Irritation Test

Table: Irritation Test

Irritation Test		
Test	Duration (Minute)	Results
T1	30	No
T2	30	No
T3	30	No
T4	30	No

Evaluation Parameter

Table: Evaluation Parameters of Anti-Ageing Cream

Evaluation Parameters of Anti-Ageing Cream		
S.No	Parameters	Observation
1	State	Semisolid
2	Colour	Off white
3	Odor	Flowery
4	Texture	Creamy
5	Consistency	Good
6	PH	6
7	Homogeneity	Good
8	Spread ability	10.23(gm.cm/sec).
9	Washability	Easily and readily washable

The usage of natural cosmetics has increased many folds in the personal care system and there is a great demand for herbal cosmetics. The use of bioactive ingredients in cosmetics influences the biological functions of the skin and provides nutrients necessary for healthy skin. The anti-ageing cream slows down skin aging by regenerating and activating the cells and protecting against ultraviolet rays, free radicals, etc. As artificial creams give many side effects it's better to use cream prepared with natural ingredients as it does not show any side effects but rather is beneficial to the skin. The results demonstrated that the formulated anti-aging creams are safe and usable for the skin. The results showed that the formulation of poly herbal antiaging cream contains all the good characteristics of an ideal cream it was found to be harmless, more effective, easy to manufacture, and more economical compared to synthetic antiaging cream.

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CONCLUSION

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